

**PERSONAL SECURITY LEVELS OF WOMEN EMPLOYEES IN THE ORGANIZED
RETAIL SECTOR**

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Abstract

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In India brick n mortar retailing employs more women than men in a 60:40 split, where women work at various levels and departments, especially on the shop floor. Contextually, personal security has become central to the physical, intellectual, emotional, economic and spiritual well-being of female employees. Various such concerns including work stress, working conditions & timings, discrimination by counterparts, fear of sexual harassment, oppressive social norms and various other factors lead women to switch jobs quite often. This study seeks to address the aforementioned challenge, and pave way for organizations to develop a retention strategy. The aim of this study is to explore and identify the various factors responsible for insecurity among women in the retail sector. By using a structured questionnaire data collected from 341 respondents, was further analyzed using SPSS 23.0 by employing factor analysis. The findings the physical, psychological and social factors impacting insecurity and offer impactful insights from a managerial, theoretical and social perspective.

Keywords: Retail; Women Employees; Workplace Security; Work-Life Balance; Sexual Harassment

Introduction

Indian Retail Sector and Women

The most active and quickly developing sector of the Indian economy is the retail sector. Numerous international businesses are making investments in the Indian retail industry. The retail industry in India contributes 8% of all jobs and 10% of the nation's GDP (Chaudhary, Sodani, and Das, 2020). As per researchers, the Indian retail area would extend to \$2 trillion by 2032 due to socio-demographic and financial factors like urbanization, pay development, and an expansion in atomic families (Krishnamurthy & Venkitachalam, 2023). The Indian web-based business market, then again, is expected to reach \$350 billion by 2030 while extending at a CAGR of 23% (Jayashree & Abirami, 2022). The online business represented about 33% of deals in various electronic classifications in the primary portion of 2021. Buyer web and web-based business organizations brought US\$38 billion up in 2021, up from US\$8 billion in 2020, as the Indian beginning up biological system proceeds to create and huge scope speculations are made in the fintech, hyperlocal, and web-based business sectors. By 2030, India will have a projected yearly gross product worth \$350 billion, making it the third-biggest internet-based retail industry (Vyas et al., 2023). The retail business in India is by and large chaotic. The level of contemporary retail, which incorporates web-based business, will ascend to 30-35% during the following 3-5 years, while the portion of traditional retail will decline to 65-70%.

India is ranked as the fifth-largest international destination in the retail industry. Due to extensive

investment in this industry and a rise in Internet users, India is predicted to be the fastest-expanding e-commerce market in the world. High hopes have been expressed by several entities for the development of the Indian e-commerce industry (Kamath & Pawar, 2022). For instance, the Indian D2C (Direct to Consumer) market is predicted to surpass sixty billion USD by 2027 (P. Gupta, 2022). All of these advancements help get jobs in the retail sector, but the employment rate for women in this sector is only growing at a moderate rate. Although women fill a range of positions in retail, their numbers frequently do not rise positively. This undesirable outcome is due to several factors. The retail industry employs the majority of women, and an equality policy may help them (Rho et al., 2020).

Challenges Women Face In the Retail Sector

The status of women in the workplace has never been higher in the modern world. They continue to live side by side with their opposite gender. However, if a woman is working (going outside to earn money), she is required to fulfill a variety of activities, such as taking care of the family, working at family centers, and so on. Working women refer to people who hold paid employment, such as secretaries, teachers, attorneys, attendants, specialists, and other wage earners. These days, women participate in every line of work (Haghighat, 2002). However, the data indicates that working women must resolve sex-related concerns in a sex-neutral manner. Women have been subjected to deceit for a very long time, and they have truly been tortured both physically and mentally. There are several challenges and obstacles that they deal with at both home and at work, some of which are explained here. A segregated workplace. At each stage of their functional circle, women are separated. At employment, they are typically excluded from promotions and educational opportunities (Ruwali, 2018). According to the Equal Remuneration Act of 1976, a larger percentage of working women continue to be denied their right to approach pay and are underpaid in comparison to their male spouses. This is frequently the case with manufacturing facilities, labor-focused businesses, etc. They are frequently refused important assignments because their scholastic degree is underestimated (Welle & Heilman, 2005). The traditional viewpoint of Indian culture frequently makes it difficult for a professional woman to reconcile her upbringing with a successful life. Working past six o'clock might not be suitable for certain families. The public will cast doubt on a woman's nobility and morals if she stays after the end of the workday. Additionally, occasionally people debate whether or not to work late owing to their unstable social situation (Trinkenreich et al., 2022). At the moment, women are seeking to financially support their male partners. Despite her unwavering dedication to the family, the image of a woman as a housewife isn't much different. Regardless of whether she works, she is required to cook meals, take care of the kids, and attend to any unfinished business from the family. Her ability to live in peace, repose, and luxury is denied by this hectic schedule (Xu, Kee, and Mao, 2021).

Security Challenges Women Face in the Retail Sector

The average percentage of women working in around one hundred and fourteen countries is around 40 percent. The test coincides with the preparations for International Women's Day, which this year focuses on orientation correspondence in the workplace (Parveen, 2022). According to the UN, elements including a fair salary distribution and unpaid labor (such as cooking and child care) are essential for achieving this goal; another important component is having an equal proportion of individuals in the workforce (Jokubauskaitė & Schneebaum, 2022). The top five countries with notable female offers are all from sub-Saharan Africa. Women make up almost half of the labor force in Tanzania, Malawi, Zimbabwe, the Gambia, and Liberia. Furthermore, at least 40% of the workforce is

female in every sub-Saharan country where information is available (Thaddeus et al., 2022).

Steps to Improve Women's Security

One of the eight important human rights concerns we've identified is harassment. Women have the right to be free from violence, harassment, and discrimination, and by removing obstacles that keep them from working in risky circumstances, they may develop as people and contribute to the workforce, their communities, and the economy. However, according to the World Health Organization, roughly one in three women (35%) experience un-partnered sexual assault or lifetime intimate partner physical and/or sexual abuse (World Health Organization (WHO), 2018). The WHO study found that the cost of violence against women is around US \$ 1.5 trillion per year or nearly 2% of the global GDP. The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) of the United Nations, particularly SDG 5 on gender equality, decent work conditions, and economic development, acknowledge the significance of defending women's rights (SDG 8). In the workplace and across the supply chain, we advocate for women's safety. With an emphasis on tackling negative societal and cultural norms and behaviors that might threaten women, our objective is to develop rules and procedures that women can trust. Work closely with partners, including our suppliers, to address issues of women's safety and fight discrimination, in addition to a variety of initiatives to address inequity and challenge damaging gender stereotypes (Diaz-Sarachaga, Jato-Espino, and Castro-Fresno, 2018).

Objectives of the Study

The primary objective of this study is to explore factors that are responsible for insecurity among women employees in the retail sector, secondly, this study will validate the variables that are associated with insecurity of female employees at work, the third objective is to suggest measures that could help women employees to practice and organizations incorporate for a long term work-relationship and a safe place for individuals to work.

Review of Literature

Problems of Working Women

Challenges faced by working women create more stress and affect their health negatively both physical and mental health (McKinsey & Company, 2022). These working women are unable to meet the family commitment as well as professional responsibilities. Thus, it becomes a major challenge for them. Working mothers as childbearing employees encounter several challenges in their children's sickness. It is also true that working mothers' challenges depend on the nature of the work they are involved in (Begeny et al., 2020).

Generally, women are associated with household chores in every household and are backed by multiple responsibilities of their family. Women are meant for making their home and holding it together, this idea of women managing their households and working within their family system is not a modern adaptation but an ancient culture. However, considering the modern equality norms, women have come forward and are still looking forward to working in any organization of their choice (Begeny et al., 2020). The changing social dynamics have worked wonders for women and helped them to be a workforce in huge numbers. Considering this sharp inclination towards the women workforce, there has to be symmetry or stability between two disciplines, the personal as well as professional role. This expert job has prompted various job stresses among working women (Swanson, 2000). The female workforce experiences a lot more roles than a male counterpart, it creates a challenging platform to

perform on and to deal with the dual functions. A study from other countries shows that generally female employees and managers are often more susceptible to additional pressure and stress from both their private and professional environment than male employees (Ibarra et al., 2013).

Women's Participation in the Retail Sector Workforce

A study by Huang, Xing, and Gamble, (2019), highlighted the role of retail in influencing stress in the workforce and the changes in attitudes related to jobs. Two specific elements such as “job fit and professional fit” were introduced to analyze the transformation from the technical view to satisfaction of the job of an individual. Prasad And Sandhyavani, (2019), analyzed to understand the role of demographic variables and stress and satisfaction on employee engagement levels in the retail sector. The results indicated while there was no interrelation between age and gender on the engagement of employees however job stress had a notable impact on job satisfaction. Sinha and Bhatt, (2020), in this article authors took a study on working women in the IT industry. They revealed that many factors demotivated female employees to continue their job. Cultural factors, society, organizational structure, organizational policies, personal issues, and insecurities are some major factors that become obstacles in front of working women to continuing their job. Prithi and Vasumathi, (2020), in this article the authors found that demographic factors like age, marital status, job position, kids, education, etc put an impact on the work-life balance of working women. Proper training has a positive influence on job satisfaction. They also found that the work-life balance and job satisfaction of a working woman are greatly influenced by organizational policy.

Factors Responsible for Insecurity among Working Women

Job Satisfaction (JS) has been elucidated as a “pleasurable or positive emotional state resulting from the appraisal of one's job or job experience”. As per the author, JS refers to an interpretation of positive thoughts for one's job. Job satisfaction refers to an overall amount of positive feelings that individuals have for their job. “It is a positive emotional state of an individual when a person is content provided the job values are compatible with his needs”(Locke, 1969).

The various dimensions or determinants of job satisfaction which make the employees satisfied or dissatisfied with their jobs can be broadly categorized under three heads:

- a) Organizational factors.
- b) Personal factors or individual factors
- c) Environmental / Technological factors.

Research Gap

There have been several studies that have different aspects related to this research. They are as follows. Literature on working women in general, the retail sector, and women's participation in the retail sector. The study also takes into consideration literature on work-life balance, stress during COVID 19 pandemic, and stress on women retail employees during COVID-19 pandemic. Having taken into consideration all the pieces of research literature the study finds that there is very less importance on “**insecurity as a challenge to women working in the retail sector**”. Hence the conclusion has been reached that the focus needs to be on female employees working in the retail sector.

Research Methodology

The variables used in the study for further analysis with the help of reliability and validity tests. They have differing viewpoints on the options presented, implying that all respondents from various companies have different opinions on the options (Abeysekera, 2019)..

Fig. 1: Proposed Research Model

Target Respondents and Sampling

In this study, the challenges of insecurity are measured among the employees of the retail sector of Odisha. So, the respondents are identified from this group only. The respondents are representative and they belong to two groups created for the study. These two groups are married and unmarried employees. The retail firms were identified, and a convenience sampling technique is applied to identify the study districts, i.e. Khordha and Cuttack. Among these regions, convenience sampling is applied to identify the study units in target retail firms. Employees were surveyed who were aged between 21 to 51 years.

Questionnaire Design and Data Collection

In this study, the questionnaire is organized into the following sections, viz. Part-1 and Part-2 Part-1 mainly comprises general and demographic information about the respondents. In this section, the researcher used a nominal scale, as this will justify the nature of the information sought through the questionnaire. In Part-2, the researcher used a five-point Likert-type Scale. In the following section, a set of statements are developed, and tests were carried out with the same. In this section, the objective is to understand the disengagement among the target respondents. The responses collected through google forms have been analyzed and the outcome of the same has been duly noted in the study.

Formulation of Research Hypothesis

H1 Physical Factors at workplace impact workplace insecurity significantly

H2 Psychological Factors have a significant and positive impact on workplace insecurity

H3 Social Factors have a significant and positive impact on workplace insecurity

Research Variables

The complete questionnaire was broken into about five sections, as seen below:

A) Respondents Profile

Variables	No. of Items	Adapted From
B) Psychological Factors	5	Lee et al. (2018)
C) Physical Factors	5	Khubchandani and Price (2017)
D) Social Factors	3	Shoss (2017)
E) Workplace Insecurity Factors	4	Cheng at al. (2011)

Demographic Characteristics

Table 1 Demographics Characteristics of the Respondents

		Frequency	Percent
Marital Status	Unmarried	167	49.0
	Married	174	51.0
Age Group	Below 18	24	7.0
	18 - 28	112	32.8
	29 - 39	169	49.6
	40 - 50	23	6.7
	Above 50	13	3.8
Monthly Income	5000-10000	76	22.3
	10001-15000	65	19.1
	15001-20000	167	49.0
	Above 20000	33	9.7
Education	<10th	16	4.7
	10th	86	25.2
	12th	152	44.6
	Graduation	69	20.2
	Post-Graduation	18	5.3

Data Analysis

Table 2 KMO and Bartlett's Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.881
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	4158.563
	df	153
	Sig.	.000

As shown in Table 2 above a KMO value of 0.881 indicates that the data is adequate for conducting factor analysis.

Exploratory Factor Analysis

Table 3 Goodness-of-fit Test

Chi-Square	df	Sig.
155.169	87	.000

Table 4 Factor Loadings

	Factor			
	1	2	3	4
PH1	.794			
PH2	.926			
PH3	.881			
PH4	.883			
PH5	.801			
WS1			.777	
WS2			.828	
WS3			.905	
WS4			.930	
PS1		.884		
PS2		.800		
PS3		.730		
PS4		.794		
PS5		.679		
SC1				.829
SC2				.780
SC3				.742
SC4				.717

From the above PCA/factor analysis we found all items that are reliable and which can be further validated by hypothesis testing and followed by linear regression.

Reliability Statistics (Cronbach Alpha)

Table 5 Scale Reliability

α (Physical Factors)	No. of Items
.747	5
α (Psychological Factors)	No. of Items
.820	5
α (Social Factors)	No. of Items
.886	3
α (Workplace Insecurity)	No. of Items
.933	4

The Cronbach Alpha Values for each construct is above the recommended level of 0.70.

Confirmatory Factor Analysis

TABLE 6 Convergent and Discriminant Validity

	CR	AVE	PHY	PSY	WIS	SOC
PHY	0.934	0.740	0.860			
PSY	0.887	0.613	0.342***	0.783		
WIS	0.921	0.746	0.320***	0.358***	0.864	
SOC	0.825	0.612	0.110†	0.401***	0.117†	0.783

The results illustrated in the above table suggest good “convergent validity” based on the Average Variance Derived (AVE) and Composite Reliability (CR) values obtained in our study (Fornell and Larcker, 1981; Bagozzi and Yi, 2012). As seen in the above table, “the square root of the AVE (represented diagonally with bold values) exceeded the inter-construct correlations” suggesting an acceptable degree of discriminant validity, thereof. The model fit statistics are illustrated in the subsequent section (Fornell and Larcker, 1981; Henseler, Ringle, and Sarstedt, 2012)

Table 7 Measurement Model-Fit Measures

Fit Indices	Values	Threshold
CMIN	216.742	--
DF	113	--
CMIN/DF	1.918	Between 1 and 3
CFI	0.973	>0.95
SRMR	0.044	<0.08
RMSEA	0.052	<0.06
PClose	0.366	>0.05

As shown in Table 7 above the obtained values for various fit indices, it is ascertained that the model and data fit well hence the model is retained for “structural modeling” (Hu and Bentler, 1999).

Structural Equation Modeling

Table 8 Structural Model-Fit Measures

Fit Indices	Values	Threshold
CMIN	323.606	--
DF	132	--
CMIN/DF	2.452	Between 1 and 3
CFI	0.953	>0.95
SRMR	0.047	<0.08
RMSEA	0.065	<0.06
PClose	0.203	>0.05

As shown in Table 8 given above, the results suggest that the proposed model was a good fit (Hu and Bentler, 1999 ; Chau, 1997; Bentler, 1990) .

Table 9 Results of Hypothesis Testing

Path			Hypothesis	Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Result
WIS	<---	PHY	H1	.183	.045	4.039	***	Supported
WIS	<---	PSY	H2	.288	.063	4.553	***	Supported
WIS	<---	SOC	H3	-.034	.087	-.394	.693	Not Supported

Further, the proposed hypotheses were tested through path analysis, all the hypothesis were tested. As outlined in the Table above, the standardized path coefficients and the p-values indicate that H1 and H2 are supported. Similarly, the standardized path coefficient and the p-values indicate for the path between SOC – WIS indicate that H3 is not supported.

Conclusion

Working should find a way to overcome the feeling of insecurity and improve their own life. Women are experts in their own experiences, priorities, and needs. They are empowered to lead their lives and determine their future. We learn from history that if we support and empower women, then everyone benefits, and society will become more stable, safe, and prosperous. They can overcome the feeling of insecurity you are facing by achieving greater autonomy and breaking free of limitations and choosing the freedom you deserve. Knowing how to build an ecosystem in this country or the workplace encourages incubation, innovation, and nurturing of entrepreneurs/organizations by following the process of educating, and giving proper training and awareness. They need to become empowered against domestic and workplace violence. They should be aware of their legal rights and learn how to find counseling and support. They should be financially independent and mentally strong. They should not allow anyone to interfere in their own life unnecessarily. During the lockdown period sought advice from professional counselors and legal experts and that is 100% confidential and secure or she can consult with any nearby legal expert or a counselor. A supportive and compassionate counselor plays a very vital role in helping the victims of role conflict. Further, all should ensure gender equality, equal pay for equal work, equal leadership opportunities, feeling and concern about motherhood, and prevention of any kind of harassment including sexual harassment to make the workplace safe, secure, peaceful, protected, free from all fear and a healthy environment for the working women.

To distinguish whether insecurity was a cause of the relationship and reported that the presence of insecurity appears to become a challenge for the participants of the survey to deal with the interface of their work and family lives. Married women and unmarried women are found to have an equal perception of insecurity and have no indifference towards factors relating to insecurity Opinion about insecurity has a p-value of 0.417 which indicates there is no difference of opinion between married and unmarried women employees relating to insecurity. We can conclude that from Levene’s t-test, we have found that there is no difference between the perception of married and unmarried women about insecurity among retail women employees.

Limitations of the Study and Future Research Directions

The survey was limited to retail employees, of Khorda and Cuttack district and it was conducted between the ages of 18 and 60 other employees may be directly or indirectly associated with retail who belong to the age group above 60 years and they could not be considered for the study. Obtaining information from the respondents belonging to the age group of above 60 years was a difficult process for the researcher owing to respondents' unwillingness to fill out the questionnaire due to the sensitive nature of the comments expressed in the questionnaire. Information supplied by respondents may be prejudiced. Even though considerable effort has been taken to ensure precision, there are still a few setbacks that need to be achieved by future studies. Future research studies can be carried out for male employees in the retail sector. There is future scope for the study of retail organizations in Odisha and other states. Research can be carried out for the non-retail sectors such as healthcare, education, hospitality, etc.

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